

Spatio-temporal assessment of human-wolf conflict in the periphery of Deosai National Park, Gilgit Baltistan, Pakistan

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Livestock depredation
Non-invasive sampling
Carnivore diet
Human-carnivore
coexistence

ABSTRACT

Apex predators, such as wolf (*Canis lupus*), play a crucial role in maintaining ecosystem balance. In Pakistan, two wolf subspecies, *Canis lupus pallipes* (Indian grey wolf) and *Canis lupus chanco* (Tibetan wolf), inhabit diverse landscapes. Despite their ecological importance, limited information exists regarding their ecology, dietary preferences, and conflicts with anthropoids in Deosai National Park, one of the largest national parks, and its surrounding areas. This study, conducted from June 2022 to December 2023, investigates the extent and prevalence of human-wolf conflicts, as well as their causes and consequences. Data collection involved structured questionnaires (n = 350 respondents) and scat sampling (112 samples from 85 locations). Human-wolf conflict was biologically assessed using scat analysis, a widely used non-invasive method for carnivore diet studies, involving 112 samples from 85 locations. The analysis revealed predation on 12 prey species, including domestic and wild animals. Domestic species constituted 52.85% of the wolf's diet, with *Ovis aries* (sheep) being the most consumed. Factors contributing to increased conflict levels included habitat destruction, wolf population growth, and depletion of natural wild prey. This study shows that livestock depredation by wolves ignites human-wolf conflict, which prejudices conservation efforts. These findings provide valuable insights into the complex dynamics of human-wolf conflict in Deosai National Park and highlight the need for informed conservation efforts and sustainable coexistence strategies to protect both wolf populations and local livelihoods.

Received: 31 January 2026; revised: 18 April 2026; accepted: 20 April 2026; and published online: 1 May 2026.

How to cite: Ali, M., Raza, G., Mehmood, T., Ali, E., Akbar, M., Ali, S., Askari, M., & Sheraz, A. (2026). Spatio-temporal assessment of human-wolf conflict in the periphery of Deosai National Park, Gilgit Baltistan, Pakistan, Sustainability and Biodiversity Conservation, 5(1): 59-79, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20003436>

Introduction

Large carnivores hold a crucial role in ecosystems as top predators, serving as foundational species. They play a critical role in ecosystem balance by regulating the populations of various species, particularly their prey (Khan et al., 2019). Global instances of conflicts between large predators and human populations are widespread (Bisi et al., 2007). The issue of human-wolf conflict is a matter of significant concern in various regions worldwide, primarily stemming from livestock predation (Ali et al., 2016). When there is a cohabitation of humans and wildlife in the same ecosystem, there is a propensity for conflicts to emerge (Tafesse, 2020). "Human-wildlife conflicts" (HWCs), denoting conflicts between human communities and wild fauna, are notably prevalent, particularly in the peripheral zones of protected habitats (Din et al., 2019; Matseketsa et al., 2019). The coexistence of humans and large carnivores faces significant challenges due to the predatory behavior of these carnivores (Mohammadi et al., 2021). While large predators play a crucial role in ecological dynamics, they are currently facing the threat of extinction worldwide (Davoli et al., 2022). The Indian grey wolf (*Canis lupus pallipes*) serves as the primary apex predator in India's semi-arid terrain. These carnivores have extensive home ranges and predominantly thrive outside of protected areas. To meet their nutritional requirements, they often prey on cattle, leading to direct conflicts with humans. This puts the identification and conservation of wolf-inhabited regions at risk (Mahajan et al., 2021). The IUCN Red List, as reported by Boitani et al. (2018), categorizes the grey wolf as "Least Concern," indicating a stable global distribution (Mahmood et al., 2022). However, in Pakistan, the status of the grey wolf is classified as "Endangered" (Boitani et al., 2018; Sheikh & Molur, 2004). In Asia, two distinct subspecies have been identified: *C. l. pallipes*, which spans the majority of the Asian region from Israel to China, and *C. l. arabs*, found in the Arabian Peninsula. Additionally, Himalayan wolves have been recognized as a separate subspecies, *C. l. chanco* (Boitani et al., 2018). In Pakistan, two wolf species have been documented: the grey wolf (*Canis lupus pallipes*) and the Tibetan wolf (*Canis lupus chanco*). In Pakistan, the grey wolf can be found spanning from the southern deserts to the northern mountains (Khattak et al., 2022; Rehman et al., 2021).

The grey wolf (*Canis lupus* Linnaeus, 1758), belonging to the Canidae family, is present throughout Pakistan, as indicated by Ali et al. (2016). Genetic research employing mitochondrial and nuclear markers has demonstrated that the Himalayan wolf is distinguishable from other grey wolf populations (Aggarwal et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2022). Unfortunately, there has been limited

research on the ecology of grey wolves in the country, resulting in a lack of comprehensive knowledge about their ecological traits and conservation requirements. Furthermore, the species faces a significant threat of extinction due to instances of livestock depredation occurring in various regions of the country (Mahmood et al., 2022). The grey wolf (*Canis lupus*), once widespread across vast regions, now predominantly occupies remote and isolated locations. Despite the wolf populations in various Asian countries being among the most endangered and data-deficient, research on them remains limited in comparison to North America and Europe. This knowledge gap is particularly significant in Pakistan, where many of its major carnivore species have become extinct (Hamid et al., 2019). Livestock depredation by wolves (*Canis lupus*) represents a prevalent source of conflict in regions where wolves and domestic animals coexist (DeCesare et al., 2018). It becomes problematic when the predator population expands and shares its habitat with particular prey species and human populations. In such scenarios, predators view domesticated animals as convenient prey, especially when their wild prey is scarce (Ali et al., 2016). The predation of livestock by mammalian predators results in substantial economic losses for marginalized farmers worldwide and triggers conflicts between humans and wildlife. These conflicts exert a significant negative impact on carnivore conservation efforts and often lead to retaliatory killings (Ullah et al., 2024; Bano et al., 2021). The main cause of conflict between people and animals is livestock predation, which is also one of the largest obstacles to the preservation of predators that inhabit areas where grazing is permitted. Major threats to carnivores included reciprocal killing, habitat destruction, and climate change (Bano et al., 2021).

Predation on cattle is the primary source of conflict between humans and canids. Because of wolf predation on livestock, pastoral communities suffer huge economic losses, particularly in areas where livestock is the sole source of income (Khattak et al., 2022). While these losses may seem insignificant on a national scale, they bear substantial consequences in rural regions. In DNP, Livestock depredation is a major issue. Culling of predators is a common strategy used to prevent damage. Increasing human population pressure and land development have resulted in shrinking and even local extinctions (Fida et al., 2024). The current study was conducted to gain knowledge about the current status of the human-wolf conflict in three buffer zones of Deosai National Park (Dapa-Katisho, Shila, and Sadpara), its causes, and its consequences.

Materials and Methods

Study area

This study was conducted in the three buffer valleys (Dapa-Katisho, Shila, and Sadpara) of Deosai National Park (DNP), Gilgit Baltistan, Pakistan. Deosai National Park is a high-altitude plateau located in northern Pakistan with coordinates at 35.02°N, 75.025°E (Figure 1). It covers an area of approximately 1400 square kilometers and has an average elevation of 4114 meters above sea level. The park extends across three districts: Astor, Kharmang, and Skardu. In the periphery of Deosai National Park, there are several primary settlements comprising Shila, Dapa, Sadpara Shingo, Gultari, and Chillam. Shila is located at an elevation of 3252 meters above sea level on the left bank of the Shila River. This community has around 85 homes, and the residents primarily engage in agro-pastoral activities, cultivating crops such as potatoes, peas, and barley. Dapa Village stands as the most elevated settlement within the Katisho Valley, found along the right bank of the Katisho River, positioned at an impressive altitude of 3886 meters above sea level. This community comprises 180 households, and its residents are engaged in various livelihood activities, primarily revolving around small-scale agriculture. The inhabitants of Dapa are dedicated to cultivating crops such as wheat, potatoes, and peas, while also participating in herding practices. Sadpara is located close to the northern entrance of Deosai National Park, at an altitude of 2350 meters above sea level, along the banks of the Sadpara River. The principal sources of income for the residents of this area encompass a diverse range of economic activities. These activities include trekking services, herding, government contract work, and small-scale agricultural endeavors.

Distribution Pattern of the Wolf

In Pakistan, the two wolf subspecies documented are the grey wolf (*C. lupus pallipes*) and the Tibetan wolf (*C. lupus chanco*). This study focuses on both subspecies inhabiting the periphery of Deosai National Park. In the current study, we used the ‘Sign and Survey’ method followed by (Baker and Leberg, 2018; Karanth et al., 2011; Gopal et al., 2010; Thorn et al., 2010) to determine the distribution of wolves in the study area. Carnivores often leave signs of characteristic appearance that indicate their presence (Wilson & Delahay, 2001). To confirm its presence in the study area, the verification involves various indicators, such as den counts, scat, deceased individuals, hair samples, and records of prey consumed. The positive site locations were recorded

using a Global Positioning System (GPS), specifically the Garmin eTrax Vista device. These coordinates were subsequently employed to create a distribution map of wolves in the study area through the use of ArcGIS.

Figure 1. (a) Map of Pakistan showing Gilgit Baltistan. (b) Map of Gilgit Baltistan (c) Map of the study area showing the three buffer valleys of DNP.

Data collection

Structured interviews, which had previously been conducted by several academics, were done as part of the data-gathering process (Bano et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2014). During the survey, a total of 350 herders and local farmers out of the total population (3000) were selected from three buffer

valleys of Deosai National Park (DNP). We used a simple random sampling method (Khan et al., 2014; Wegge et al., 2012) for structured interviews held from June 2022 to December 2023. The number of respondents was determined using Yamane's formula. Respondents, both male and female, having at least 3 years 'experience of pastoral life and herding on pastures, were contacted in person and interviewed. Various open and closed-ended questions from the questionnaire were first read and explained, and then suitable responses were recorded promptly. Supplementary information acquired during the interview was also documented in the notebook. Questions were asked to get data about the household demography, education, source of income, and number of livestock lost to predators. Perceived problem carnivores: resource use and conservation issues. Livestock owners' perception of the conflict, losses caused by predators, and their attitude towards carnivores were queried during the talk. For every animal lost, species, year, season, place, and predator species were documented. Herders were also interrogated about the extent of predation, potential mitigation methods, and their opinions about protection from predators.

Scat Analysis

Biologically, the extent of human-wolf conflict in the study area was determined by scat analysis (Khan et al., 2020). The diet composition of a wolf was investigated by using a non-invasive method of analysis of their scat samples, followed by (Akrim et al., 2019; Mahmood et al., 2021a).

Scat Collection and Identification

For this purpose, scat samples were procured from June 2022 to December 2023. Any scat that was discovered encountered in the field was subject to immediate morphological inspection, which included its diameter, length, shape, color, odor, and physical properties like contents (hair and bones) (Akrim et al., 2019). Scat samples from different sites were collected and stored in polyethylene bags, which were marked with dates, the name of the site, landscape types, age of scat, and GPS coordinates. To minimize the risk of fading the basic information, a water-resistant pen was used.

Diet Analysis

The physical features of scat samples, like length, breadth, and weight, were measured using a digital Vernier caliper (Neiko 01407A) and a digital electronic weighing balance, followed by (Špinkytė-Bačkaitienė & Pėtelis, 2012), in the Mammalian Ecology and Conservation Laboratory of PMAS- Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi. For further analysis, the samples were soaked in distilled water for 24 hours. After that, the samples were washed with tap water using a 0.5mm

mesh-sized sieve to remove debris, mucous sand, etc. (Liu & Jiang, 2003). The washed material was kept in the drying oven (Contherm-7100) for drying at 30 °C for 8 hours. After that, different constituents of scats like hair, bones, teeth, seeds, sands, clay, and plant materials were segregated using a hand lens 10X (Ciucci et al., 1996). The weight of different constituents of scat, like hair, bones, seeds, plant material, and other unidentified constituents, was also documented using a digital micro-balance at the Central Laboratory of PMAS- Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi. The hair remains of prey were used to identify the prey species (Mahmood et al., 2022). The remains of prey, such as hair in scat samples, were used for the identification of unknown prey species, using the procedure and protocol described by Klare et al. (2011).

Whole Mount Preparation

For identifying types of mammalian prey, we employed hairs. Microscopic slides of several prey species' hairs were created for this purpose. Carbon tetrachloride and ethanol were used to wash hair for up to 20 minutes. Small chunks of long hair were chopped out, and twisted hair was removed. We used clear nail paint to prepare the whole mount. The medullary pattern and cuticle cast pattern of the hairs recovered from scat samples were used to ascertain the prey species of the wolf. The identity of the prepared slides was then confirmed by comparing them with reference hair slides. For this purpose, a reference hair sample of a potential prey wolf was collected from the Pakistan Museum of Natural History, Islamabad, Pakistan. Using a light microscope at magnifications of 10x, 40x, and 100x connected with the camera and monitor, the slides were compared (Ciucci et al., 1996; Mahmood et al., 2021a).

Scale replication

The cuticular scale patterns of mammalian prey hairs were examined using a method involving several steps. Initially, two to three drops of clear nail polish were evenly applied to a glass slide. A small hair was then positioned upright along the slide's axis. Once the nail polish had dried, the exposed end of the hair was carefully removed in a single motion using forceps, creating a cast of the hair on the nail polish. This cast was an accurate replica of the hair's scales and was analyzed under a microscope, comparing it to a reference for identification (Akrim et al., 2019).

Prey Identification

The prey species were determined through a comparative analysis of cuticular attributes of the hairs, encompassing factors such as scale locus, scale arrangement, scale margin, and the gap between scale margins. Likewise, medullary characteristics, including width composition,

structural attributes, and cross-sectional shape of the recovered hairs from the scats, were juxtaposed with a photographic reference hair guide. Following a thorough examination of the hairs using this photographic reference key, the prey items within the scat samples were overwhelmingly identified. Subsequently, these identified prey species were categorized into two groups: domestic animals and wild animals.

Statistical Analysis

The percentage frequency of prey species in the wolf's diet was determined through calculations performed using MS Excel. This frequency of occurrence signifies how often the prey was encountered and indicates its relative importance in the wolf's diet. The data were organized into tables, and the relative frequency (RF), which is the number of times each prey species occurred when present, divided by the total number of occurrences of all prey species, was calculated as a percentage. For the questionnaire-based survey, SPSS 22.0 software was employed for data analysis. The statistical analysis of the survey was conducted through descriptive statistics. Additionally, the relationship between variables in the questionnaire-based survey was assessed using the Pearson correlation test, which was performed with the assistance of SPSS.

Results

Distribution of Wolf

The distribution of wolves was surveyed in the three buffer valleys (Dapa-Katisho, Shila, and Sadpara) of Deosai National Park for recording data on wolf indirect and direct sightings and signs. 'Sign and survey method' was used to evaluate the distribution of wolves in the study area. The three buffer valleys of Deosai National Park were documented as positive for the presence of wolf signs. The scat of the wolf was collected from a total of 85 locations in these buffer valleys. The highest number of 42 scats was collected from 6 tracks in Shila Valley. About 36 scat samples were collected from 6 tracks of Dapa Valley. 34 scat samples were collected from 05 tracks of Sadpara Valley. The pugmarks of the wolf were observed at Rebo-Nala of Shila Valley, Throny Thang of Dapa Valley, and Marfo-La. The snow tracks of the suit species were also recorded at Koshoq-Nala, Choga-lungba, and Sadpara top. A dent of a wolf was observed in Shila Valley. The howling of the wolf was also heard in Dapa Valley during our night stay while collecting scat samples. The GPS coordinates of positive spots for indirect signs of the presence of a wolf are shown in the table:

Scat Analysis

The nature and extent of depredation and dietary habits of wolves were analyzed by the non-invasive scat analysis. A total of 112 scat samples were collected and analyzed in the Mammalian Ecology and Wildlife Management Laboratory of PMAS-Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Morphological Features of Wolf Scat

Morphologically, the scats were pointed at both ends and broader at the middle with nodes. The average length was 24.24cm (± 0.83). The mean breadth was 4.95375cm (± 0.35) while the average weight was 33.53g (± 1.74) (Table 1).

Table 1. Physical Parameters of Scat Samples

	Length (cm)	Breadth (cm)	Weight (gram)
Mean=	24.24470588	4.95375	33.53352941
SE	± 0.83359212	± 0.352929338	± 1.742387844

The physical measurements of scat samples closely align with those reported in studies conducted by Hamid et al. (2019). These measurements indicate that scat length fell within the range of 22.82 to 87.66 cm, breadth ranged from 9.42 to 31.47 cm, and scat weight varied between 16.75 and 169.53 g. Similar findings were observed in another study by Mahmood et al. (2022), where the mean scat length, breadth, and weight were 25.40 ± 1.12 cm, 3.15 ± 0.171 cm, and 32.18 ± 3.52 g, respectively. Furthermore, Khan et al. (2020), in their research, also reported comparable results, with mean scat weight, length, and breadth measuring at 34.43 ± 5.79 g, 26.93 ± 3.43 cm, and 3.22 ± 0.182 cm, respectively.

Diet Composition of the Wolf

Laboratory analysis of 112 collected scats of the species showed hairs, bones, seeds, plant matter, clay/sand, and unidentified matter (Table 2). Hairs were recovered from scat samples constitute 63.12%V followed by bones 12.45%V. Plant matters contributed 11.69%V, sand, and clay 5.61%V, seed 3.64%V and unidentified materials 3.47%V (Table 3).

Table 2. Macro-Components Recovered from Wolf Scats

Hairs		Bones	Seed	Plant material	sand/clay	Unidentified materials
MEAN	5.19	1.02	0.3	0.96	0.46	0.29
SE	±0.24	±0.18	±0.12	±0.21	±0.13	±0.10

Table 3. Percentage Volume and Frequency of Macro Components of Scat Samples

Item	% Volume	% Frequency
Hairs	63.12	100
Bones	12.45	82,35
Seeds	3.64	47.07
Plant Matters	11.69	64.7
Sand/clay	5.61	58.82
Others	3.47	47.05

Prey Preference and Livestock Depredation by Wolf

Laboratory analysis of scats revealed depredation of 12 prey species (6 domestic and 6 wild) by the wolf. As shown in Table 4, domestic species constituted 52.85% of the wolf's diet, with sheep (*Ovis aries*) being the most consumed domestic prey (22.05% RF). Among wild prey, the golden marmot (*Marmota caudata*) contributed the highest (14.83% RF). The remaining prey species and their relative frequencies are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Prey Preference and Livestock Depredation by Wolves

Prey Type	Prey Species	Scientific name	Class	N0. of Prey	% Frequency
Domestic Prey Species	Goat	<i>Capra aegagrus hirus</i>	Mammalia	49	18.63
	sheep	<i>Ovis aries</i>	Mammalia	58	22.05
	Domestic cow	<i>Bos taurus</i>	Mammalia	22	8.37
	Horse	<i>Equus caballus</i>	Mammalia	1	0.38
	Donkey	<i>Equus asinus</i>	Mammalia	5	1.90
	Yak	<i>Bos grunniens</i>	Mammalia	4	1.52
Wild Prey Species		Sub-total		139	52.85
	Himalayan ibex	<i>Capra ibex sibirica</i>	Mammalia	9	3.42
	Himalayan musk deer	<i>Moschus chrysogaster</i>	Mammalia	8	3.04
	Golden marmot	<i>Marmota caudata</i>	Mammalia	39	14.83
	House mouse	<i>Mus musculus</i>	Mammalia	28	10.65
	Royle's pika	<i>Ochotona roylei</i>	Mammalia	21	7.98
	Palm civet	<i>Paguma larvata</i>	Mammalia	19	7.22
		Sub-total		124	47.15

Figure 2. (1) Domestic prey species (A) Domestic Yak), (B, Goat), (C, Cow), (D, Donkey), (E, Sheep), (F, Horse) (2) Wild prey species (A, House Mouse), (B, Golden Marmot), (C, Himalayan ibex), (D, Royals Pika), (F, Himalayan musk deer), (F, Palm civet). (Note: **RS:** Reference Sample **SS:** Slide sample).

Spatio-temporal Variation in the Diet of Wolf and HWC

The results of the present study demonstrate that the diet composition of wolves shows significant seasonal variation (Figure 3). In the winter season, the domestic livestock depredation is higher than in the summer season and constitutes 69.91% of the wolf diet. Sheep was consumed highly at 33.63%. The Domestic goat made up 23.89 % of the diet in winter, followed by the Domestic cow, 9.73%. Yak contributed 2.65% of the diet in the winter season. In the winter season, the wild prey species of wolf showed a relatively smaller proportion of diet than in the summer season. The wild species constituted 30.09% of the wolf diet. Among wild species, house mice were the most abundant prey of wolves in the study area, with the highest 8.85%, followed by Golden marmot at 7.96%. Whereas Palm civet contributed 6.19%, Royal pika 4.42%, Himalayan musk 1.77%, and Himalayan ibex 0.88%. On the other hand, in summer, the domestic species constituted 40.00% and the wild prey species 60.00%. Among the domestic species, domestic goats showed the highest contribution 14.67% followed by sheep, 13.33%. Domestic cows contributed 7.33%, donkeys 3.33%, horses 0.67%, and yak 0.67 relative Frequency in the diet. Among wild species, the golden marmot showed the highest part of the wolf diet 20.00% followed by house mouse 12.00% Whereas Royle's pika and Palm civet constituted. 10.67% and 8.00 % respectively. While the Himalayan ibex is 5.33% and the Himalayan musk deer 4.00%.

Extend Spatio-temporal Human-Wolf Conflict in Three Buffer Valleys of DNP

The current study revealed that among the three buffer valleys of DNP, Dapa Valley is on top in terms of livestock depredation by wolves (Figure 4). The laboratory analysis of wolf scat results confirmed the depredation of 64 livestock in a year. The domestic sheep contributed the most with 29, followed by goats with 20, domestic cows with 11, donkeys with 2, horses with 1, and yaks with 1 in number. This study ranked Shila Valley second in terms of livestock depredation by wolves. The scat analysis of wolves confirmed the depredation of 42 cattle and livestock. Like Dapa Valley, Sheep were the highest contributor prey species of the wolf with 18 numbers in Shila Valley. Goats and domestic cows contributed 13 and 7 numbers, respectively. During the study period in the study area, the least affected area in terms of livestock depredation is Sadpara Valley, with 33 depredated livestock. Unlike the other two aforementioned buffer valleys, the top prey species of a wolf was the goat in the Sadpara Valley. The domestic goat contributed the highest part with 16, followed by sheep at 11, domestic cow at 4, donkey at 1, and yak at 1 in number.

In Dapa Valley, the domestic Livestock contributed to the diet of wolves mostly in winter 62.5% than in summer, 37.5%. In winter, the preferred prey of wolves was sheep, 14 in number, followed by goats, 18 prey species. Other domestic livestock were domestic cow (4 in summer, 7 in winter), horse (1 in summer), donkey (2 in summer), and yak (1 in winter). The extent and pattern of human-wolf conflict in terms of livestock depredation by wolves reportedly showed variation seasonally. In Shila Valley, wolves consume more livestock in winter than in summer. Out of the total depredated livestock, winter season showed 57.14% and 42.86 in summer. This included goats (5 in summer, 8 in winter), sheep (5 in summer, 13 in winter), domestic cows (5 in summer, 2 in winter), and yak (1 in winter, 1 in summer). In Sadpara Valley, the seasonal variation in livestock depredation was quite different. Out of the total livestock portion of the diet in one year, livestock contributed more in summer 54.54% than in winter, 45.45%. In the summer season, the domestic livestock depredation is higher than in the winter season. A goat was consumed highly (11 in summer and 5 in winter). Unlike goats, sheep showed a high consumption by wolves in winter (7 in winter and 4 in summer). Whereas a donkey was depredated in summer.

Figure 3. Seasonal Variation in the Diet of the Wolf

Figure 4. Livestock depredation in the Buffer Valleys of Deosai National Park

Discussion

In the present study, the pugmarks of the wolf were observed at Rebo-Nala of Shila Valley, Throny Thang of Dapa Valley, and Marfo-La. The snow tracks of the suit species were also recorded at Koshoq-Nala, Choga-lungba, and Sadpara top. A dent of a wolf was observed in Shila Valley. The howling of a wolf was also heard in Dapa Valley during our night stay. The GPS coordinates of positive sites for indirect signs of the presence of wolves are shown in Table 3. Previous studies also confirmed the presence of grey wolves (Abbas et al., 2013; Mahmood et al., 2021b) in the area. Similar results were also confirmed by Kabir et al. (2017). The grey wolf (*Canis lupus pallipes*) is a subspecies of grey wolf that extends from Southwest Asia to the Indian Subcontinent (Hamid et al., 2019).

The presence of grey wolves was also reported by (Abbas et al., 2013) in Sadpara Valley. Two subspecies of wolves occur in Pakistan, including the Indian grey wolf (*Canis lupus pallipes*) and Tibetan wolf (*Canis lupus chanco*). The Indian grey wolf is confined to remote tracks of arid hilly

regions and wide-ranging desert, open plains (semi-arid grasslands, scrublands, grazing land, etc) (Saad et al., 2015). Their territories range between 150 and 300 square kilometers (Jhala et al., 2022). Previous studies also confirmed the presence of grey wolves (Abbas et al., 2013; Mahmood et al., 2022) in the area. Similar results were also confirmed by (Kabir et al., 2017). The grey wolf (*Canis lupus pallipes*) is a subspecies of grey wolf that extends from Southwest Asia to the Indian Subcontinent (Hamid et al., 2019). The presence of the grey wolf in the Sadpara valley was also reported by Abbas et al. (2013).

The Scat analysis of wolves revealed that the domestic species made up 52.85 % of the total consumed diet, and wild species contributed 47.15 %. Among domestic species, *Ovis aries* (Sheep) contributed the most with 22.05%RF, followed by *Capra aegagrus hirus* (Domestic goat) 18.63%RF. In a prior investigation conducted in Deosai National Park by (Mahmood et al., 2022) It was determined that the wolf's diet predominantly consisted of a higher number of domestic livestock. Their findings revealed that domestic prey constituted approximately 53.57% of the wolf's diet, while wild prey accounted for 46.43%. In a study conducted in Misgar Valley by (Bano et al., 2021) out of a total of 9,273 livestock, 310 were killed by predators due to predation between 2014 and 2019. Among these losses, 168 (54%) were attributed to wolf predation. The affected livestock included sheep (35.16%), followed by goats (27.74%), domestic yaks (20.64%), and cattle (16.45%).

The diet composition of wolves significantly showed seasonal variation. In the winter season, the domestic livestock depredation is higher than in the summer season and constitutes 69.91% of the wolf diet. Sheep was consumed highly at 33.63%. The wild species constituted 30.09% of the wolf diet in the winter season. Among wild species, house mice were the most abundant prey of wolves in the study area, with the highest 8.85% relative frequency. On the other hand, in summer, the domestic species constituted 40.00% and the wild prey species 60.00%. Among the domestic species, the domestic goat showed the highest contribution, 14.67% relative frequency. Among wild species, the golden marmot showed the highest part of the wolf diet 20.00% followed by the house mouse 12.00% relative frequency. Previous literature also showed that the diet of wolves varies seasonally (Mahmood et al., 2022). Reported that the diet of grey wolves greatly varies in Deosai National Park, Pakistan. Grey wolf diet varied between winter and summer seasons. In the winter season, the depredation of livestock by grey wolves was higher than in the summer season.

It is also the reason behind the seasonal variation in the pattern of livestock depredation that in summer, wolf most live on high altitude pasture for breeding. There is a relatively greater number of wild prey species in the summer season than in winter. Secondly, in summer, intensive shepherding is ensured by the locals at high-altitude pastures in the summer season. Whereas in the winter season, after harvesting crops, the locals freed their cattle in the suburbs of villages and the periphery of DNP. That is why the depredation of livestock by wolves is reported to be most common in the peripheral settlements of DNP. In a similar study conducted in Mahood and Valley by (Khan et al.,2020) the diet of the grey wolf was examined through scat analysis. The analysis revealed the consumption of 13 prey species, comprising 5 domestic and 8 wild species. Among domestic prey, donkeys were the most frequently consumed (100% Frequency), followed by sheep (*Ovis aries*) at 24.32%, domestic cows (*Bos taurus*) at 13.51%, while horses (*Equus caballus*) and goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) made the smallest contributions. Davie et al. (2014) Conducted a study on livestock depredation by wolves in Mongolia. The report highlighted that out of the 31 pastoralists who reported predation events, 30 had experienced losses of sheep or goats.

The prey preference and pattern of livestock depredation studied by (Iliopoulos et al., 2009) in central Greece, also reported similar types of results. This current study of Human wolf conflict, wolf diet composition, and preference of wolves also confirmed that, like other geographical regions of the world, livestock is a significant part of the wolf diet. Like the previous studies in different countries, domestic sheep and goats made the highest contribution to the diet of wolves in the three buffer valleys of DNP. Bano et al. (2021) Conducted a study on livestock predation by predators in Misgar Valley, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan. They employed a semi-structured questionnaire to gather data regarding livestock numbers, depredation patterns, predation counts, and conservation strategies. Their findings indicated a statistically significant upward trend in predation incidents. Out of a total of 9,273 livestock, 310 animals were killed by predators, with an annual average of 51 animals per year. Among these, 168 (54%) were attributed to wolf predation. Key threats to predators in the area included retaliatory killings, habitat degradation, and the impact of climate change.

In response to a question, while conducting a questionnaire-based survey, most of the respondents (37.14%) considered the increased number of predators to be the major cause of livestock depredation in the area. Whereas 65.14% of respondents ranked the depredation as severe in the study area. Different coping strategies to control depredation by wolves were also reported. Some

of these are lethal to the conservation of wolves and pose a serious threat to the life of the species. Non-lethal coping strategies included intensified shepherding (29.14%) and moving livestock (23.71%). Whereas lethal control measures used by the locals are poisoning (11.71%) and shooting (6.00%).

Some of the coping strategies practiced by the local community were found to be lethal, which jeopardized the conservation efforts. A prior study conducted by (Tobajas et al., 2020) found that certain non-lethal strategies can effectively mitigate depredation under specific conditions. These non-lethal approaches have proven to be safe when dealing with certain types of predators. One promising non-lethal method proposed for deterring large carnivores from attacking livestock is conditioned food aversion (CFA). CFA occurs when an animal associates a particular food with illness, leading it to reject that food in future encounters. This aversion can be linked to the introduction of an artificial odor during the conditioning process. (Smith et al., 2016) Also devised some non-lethal coping strategies, such as Livestock custodians, Herd Supervision, Reducing Attractants, Disruptive Stimuli, Visual & Acoustic Scare Devices, Real-time Virtual Fence (RTVF) / Remote Alarm Aid, Aversive Stimuli, Boundary, and translocation are some non-lethal control techniques that can be used to reduce wolf depredation on livestock. (Gehring et al., 2006) Studied 3 non-lethal management tools (fladry, livestock guarding dogs, shock collars) relative to their effectiveness for altering wolf movements away from livestock areas. Pimenta et al. (2017) also reported that compensation for damages is one of the potential tools and operative strategies to mitigate conflicts with large carnivores, including wolves, and prevent retaliatory killing of predators.

Conclusion

There exists a severe spatiotemporal conflict between humans and wolves in the buffer valleys of DNP. The human-wolf conflict causes the failure of conservation efforts, which poses a serious threat to the endangered grey wolf and a significant economic loss to humans. The retaliatory measures and coping strategies used by the local community are lethal for the population of wolves and prejudice the efforts for the conservation of wolves in the area. Hence, a contract in the region may need to be initiated.

Recommendations

Based upon these findings, we recommend the following actions to ensure the conservation of wolves and reduce the financial loss of local farmers and herders in terms of livestock depredation:

1. An organized incentive system with ease of accessibility should be launched to compensate for the farmer's loss.
2. The community-based awareness campaign and village-level training programs should be organized for herders to reduce HWC.
3. Local herders and nomads should be restricted to certain specific grazing areas.
4. An insurance policy should be for cattle with high market value, like Yak, etc.
5. Community-based volunteer teams should be nominated under the supervision of a Village counselor to monitor the conservation and poaching of wild species.
6. The importance of apex predators and their role in balancing our ecosystem should be made part of the textbook and syllabus.
7. Strict laws and their enforcement should be practiced against hunters and poachers.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this work.

Acknowledgments

The authors are thankful for the technical support provided by the Laboratory of PMAS- Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, and the Central Laboratory of PMAS- Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. They also extend their gratitude to the respondents of the local community who shared valuable knowledge during the investigation.

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